

ON CERTAIN MILITARY TITLE IN THE CENTRAL AUTHORITY OF TURKISH EMPIRE

Dustmurodov M.M.

Doctor of philosophy (PhD) on philological sciences, associate professor

Head of Scientific Department of TIPI

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Abstract. *Titles and positions make up a significant part of the changes in the military system of the Khaganate recorded in the ancient Turkish chronicles. In this article, we covered the semantic-functional and etymological analysis of the titles related to the attack of central authority reflected in the Orkhun-Yenisei tombstones.*

Keywords: *military terms, Turkish khanate, Orkhun-Yenisei milestones, military rank.*

Among the state associations built by the Turks, the Turkic Khaganate holds a special place, in which the complete form of the ancient Turkic statehood, traditions and system of titles is clearly manifested. The process of the formation of the system of titles in the Khaganate was directly related to the development of the centuries-old statehood of Turkic peoples and the traditions of continuity of state associations in Central Asia. "In the early stages of the history of the state, there was a strict hierarchy in the ancient Turkic society, according to which the position and political weight of the member of the state society in the system of social relations was defined by his title. This situation is a unique feature of the ancient Turkic society, which is confirmed by the information of Chinese, ancient Turkic and other sources. It should be noted that referring to the system of military-administrative terms existing in Turkic Khaganate is a source that not only illuminates the state building of the Khaganate, but also has a special place in the study of its entire history.

Some military degree are included followings in Central Turkic Khanate: : *qayan* – “high governor”, *yabyu/yabyu-qayan* – “Khan/ Western wing controller”, *qan* – “leader of the nation”, *šad* – “head of the ulus, khagonzoda”, *šadapit* – “a military officer in the wings”, *tägin* – “in Khakonzoo; representative”, *ayyuči* – “adviser, prime minister”, *buyruq* – “minister, general”, *baš* – “leader”; *bašlıy* – “head, leader”, *säñün* – “commander”, *sübaši* – “army chief, commander”, *yüz baši* – “centurion”, *bäs yüz baši* – “leader for 500 people”, *biña baši* – “leader for thousand people”, *ič sü baš* – “responsible for internal order”, *yizäk baši* – “the head of the vanguard”, *bäg* – “relatively large officials”, *boyla* – “State Counselor”, *yalabač, sabčı, älči* – “ambassador”, *čabiš* – “a responsible person in the army, one of the commanders of the army”, *apatarqan* – “high-ranking commander”, *alpayut* – “the leader of the alpine warriors”, *ičräki* – “a palace official”, *čigsi / čiksi* – “military governor”, *yaryučı / yaryan* – “investigator”, *uruñu* – “flagman”, *tuğči* – I. “flagman”, II. “who plays the khagan's drum”, *boryuči* – “a driller”.

baš lexeme, whose original meaning is "the head of the being, anatomical head", as a result of the expansion of the meaning, was used to refer to the person or thing standing above the army, tribe and everything in general. The derivative of *bašlıly* used in the scriptures in the sentence " *bašlıly yüküntürmiš tiziglig sökürmiš* - the head of the head is burdened (he bowed his head)" (KT, 8) means "he has a boss - a guide". "Kutadgu bilig" mentions the expression of *bašlıly*: "Süsi başlıg ärsä er ašlıg bolur - if there is a leader in the army, the soldiers will have sustenance" (QBK, 12216). Also, in the pandnoma, there is a formation of *baščı* in the sense of a leader: " *Qalı ädgü*

bolsa bodun baščisi, qali ädǵü boldi anıñ işčisi - If the leader of the people is good, his servants will also be good" (QBN, 754; QBN, 879). According to J.Clawson, "the first meaning of the word "baş" is the head part of the human body, as it was mentioned above, and in the figurative sense it means "leader or commander of the army". H. Shirin notes that the word bash means "leader of a tribe, people, community or army". the word baş is reflected in the inscriptions as follows: " *täñri älimkä başda bägimkä bökmädim* - I have not had enough of my heavenly state, my guiding Beg" (Y, 14/3).

The lexeme *baş* in this sentence is used in the sense of "military leader, chief, warlord". In Uzbek language, the word "bosh" is interpreted in a certain place as "leader and chief", as well as "anatomical head" (O'TIL, I, 332). Mahmud Koshgari notes that in general, it occurs in the sense of "the head of a person; head (animals, plants, objects and mountain)" (DLT, III, 165; I, 365). In "Kutadgu bilig" the word " *baş* " is used in both primary and transitive meanings: " *Biligsiz sözi öz başini yäyür* – "An ignorant word eats its own head" (QBN, 253; QBN, 167); " *Näǵü tar äšitǵil ay älcü başi* - listen to what the head of the ambassadors says" (QBK, 24719).

Sübaši - "commander of the army, commander of the army": " *sü başi İnäl qayan Tarduš šad barzun tädi* - the commander of the army Inal khagan Tardush said, let him go" (Ton, 31); "... *sü başi bän* - I am the commander of the army" (MCh, 48). This term is also mentioned in "Kutadgu bilig": " *Qayusi sü başi qayusi həjib, qayusi ilimya bolur* - Which one will be the head of the army, which one will be a hajib, which one will be a sarcotib" (QBN, 2936; QBN, 2968). In the text of Mo'yun Chor, the term *biña başi* (thousand leader) is mentioned: " *biña:baši: iti* was a thousand leader" (MCh, 6). Also in the inscriptions there are terms like *bäs yüz başi, yüz başi, är başi*: " *bäs yüz başi Kül Onı: Öz inanču: bäs yüz: başi: Uluǵ Öz İnanču 7. Uruǵu: yüz: başi.. 8.....miş toquz yüz är: başi...*" (Tar, 6-8).

In the epitaphs, the combination " *ič sü baş* " with the meaning of "special army leader" is mentioned: *ič sü baş ... öl[ti]* – a special army leader died (Y, 39). In this sentence, *ič sü baş* most likely refers to the title of a military official responsible for internal order in a palace or residence, which can be understood as "commander of palace troops".

Blue Turkic inscriptions use the word *är at*, which here means "coming of age": " *inim kül tägin är at bolti* – brother Kul Tegin grew up (became a man)" (KT, 31) ; " *oylan atim čubuč inäl ärtä atim kümül öǵä* – that *är at* (manhood) given according to the qualities shown in the khagan's society was mainly considered as a nickname or an epithet. The interpretation of the verb *ärät* in "Devonu Lug`otit-Turk" (DLT, II, 215) with the meaning "counted from the lands, passed to the ranks of the lands" (DLT, II, 215) shows that the lexeme was actively used in that period as well. "According to Mahmud Koshgari, the root of the verb in question was in the form *ärüz*. The last sound of this word became *ärät* as a result of absorption into the previous sound (DLT, I, 215)". In fact, *ärät* in DLT should be exactly the combination of *ärät* in the stones. In "Kutadgu bilig" this combination is found in a different meaning, in the plural form: *ärät* - man(s), person(s), soldiers, warrior in the form: " *Bu äl tutyuqa köp ärät sü käräk* – To hold this country in hand, many warriors are needed" (QBN, 1575; QBN,).

One of the most actively used titles in Orkhun-Yenisei documents is "speaker, advisor, minister; *ayyučü* meaning "commander" is a high-ranking title. Istilah is mentioned in the inscriptions as a title belonging to Tonyuquk: " *qayani alp ärmiş, ayyučüsi bilgä ärmiş* – he is a judge of the king, and his adviser is a thinker" (Ton, 10). After Tonyuquk, no other statesman was named with this high title. *Ayyučü*, a high-ranking minister, has a number of powers and acts as a

person who advises the Khagan in the civil and military spheres. *Ayyučī* was considered a "representative and advisor of the king" as a "high rank" meaning a person who "says and gives orders". In the central administration of the West Turkic Khaganate, ministers and advisers were called *ayyučī*, *buyruq*, *ögä*. One can draw conclusions about the position and status of the holders of these positions in the khagan administration system from the sentences in the inscriptions " *If the king is a giant, his advisor is wise* ".

In the texts of the Uighur period, it is noticeable that the title of *ayyučī* partially lost its importance and fell to the level of an administrative, civil or religious title of a slightly lower rank. In particular, according to J. Clauson, "the representation of *ayg'uchi* professions as master and foreman, kitchen inspector, and revenue manager in this period shows how low he fell". " *sazin ayyučī* in Uyghur texts means "a priest, a Buddhist adviser, a secondary preacher in a temple, one who distributes duties inside and outside the temple". This name was later used in Turkic countries.

One of the most frequently used terms in the inscriptions is the military-administrative title *bäg* – "chief of the tribe or clan". In the name of most of the titles in the management of the khaganate, the duties and level of the holders of these titles are reflected. "Each official in the khaganate has a specific title, and since several dozen titles differing in terms of position are used for them, the term " *bäg* " is used to represent important officials in a general sense. *Bäg Kul* is found actively in Tegin: " *üčünč Yägän Silig bägiñ kädimlig torıy at binip tägdi* – the third (there) Yegan attacked Silig beg's clothed (armored) torik horse" (KT, 33). The place of reflection of this istilah in the writings shows that it was mainly applied to chieftains of tribes or clans. Also, in the documents there is a word derived from this word, *bäglig*, which was mainly used for boys who were worthy of being a bek within the categories. This composition is visible in the inscriptions of Kul Tegin, Bilga Khakhan and Ongin: " *Tabyač bodunqa bäglik urı oylın qul boltı* – Tabgach became a slave with a son who would be a beg (worthy of beg) for the people of Tabg'ach." (KT, 7).

G. Dörfer interprets the term *bäg* as "governor, head of a clan or a class of officials". " *Sabimın tukäti äšidgil: ulayu ini yigünüm, oylanım, biriki oyuşum bodunum, biryä šadapit bäglär, yırya tarqat buyruq bäglär* – Listen to my words! After me, my younger brother, my nephew, my son(s), my alliance clan - my people, the shadapit begs on the right, the tarkhans on the left, the command begs" (BX, 13-14). In this appeal, the meaning of the word " *bäg* " is clarified.

"In the ancient Turkish kingdom, the begs always lined up on the right (high-ranking *šadapit* (titled) *begs*) and left (*tarqat* (*tarkhans*) and order (*vizier*) *begs*) of the supreme ruler. " The above sentence and material examples from several other sources show that the begs were considered an important category between the supreme ruler and the people. The cohesion of the people and the ruler or internal disunity was mainly related to the activities of the begs. Also, " *bäg* " is recorded in the researches as "leader, noble, prince, rich, titled". In Kipchaks, the word *bäg* or *bi* means "heir to the throne".

Bäg "was a special military-administrative position that had the task of protecting the unity of the tribe, introducing laws and regulations in terms of legal and justice in the clan under his control, protecting tribal interests with weapons when necessary". The privileges of these titleholders in state management have a hereditary character, and their scope of authority has been strengthened. It should be said that "each *bek*-official had titles and nicknames classified according to his position, along with personal names associated with animal names."

In the saga "Alpomish", the genealogical functions of *bek* (*biy*) mentioned above are clearly visible: "In the past, sixteen clans were called *Dobonbiy* in the people of Kungirost. Dobonbi had a son named Alpinbi. ... And now sixteen clans have become one chuprontoy in Kungirost people. He informed the people and the Elatians to the wedding. All the people gathered for this wedding. The rich also came to the wedding." Educated and wise people were promoted to the position of beg. Yusuf Khos Hajib in his work "Kutadgu Bilig" juxtaposes the word "Bag" with the word "Bilig" (knowledge, wisdom). In the inscriptions of the Uyghur Khaganate (745-840), it was used as an *istilah*, representing a group of important officials. In particular, it is possible to witness that the words "*Töläs bäglär, Tarduš bäglär*" related to the two wings that attached several of the officials mentioned above that are used in the Taryat inscription.

In "Kutadgu bilig" words related to *bäg* are mentioned, such as *bägi* - "hero", *bäglük* - "beg, beg authority", *bägsig* - "like beg": "*Bäg atı bilig birlä baglög turur* - Bek horse is related to knowledge" (QBK, 9914); "*Süčig äsrükindä bätär ay bägi* - O hero, wine is worse than drunkenness" (QBK, 36811); "*Büzüg iştä täñsiz baş agrög bolur, baş agrög köttürmäsä bäglük kalur* - in a great work there will be incomparable hardship, if one does not bear the hardship, one will be doomed to decline forever" (QBN, 109a); "*Adırmas män bäsigs ya külsig kişig* - I do not divide people into beggars and slaves" (QBN, 688). Mahmud Koshghari also uses the word *bäg* in the meaning of "landlord, governor": "*bäg künd ägirdi* - beg besieged the city". The lexicographer writes that the same word, pronounced with a soft k, meaning "little noble" (DLT, I, 339). The widespread use of the term "*bäg*" as a military-administrative title in Turkish texts shows that it has preserved its semantic-functional position not only in the ancient stage of the Turkish language, but also in the later period.

In addition to the members of the ruling family, the central administration of the Turkish khanate - the palace also housed the military ministers represented by the order derivative. The term can be found in the Kul Tegin and Bilga khagan inscriptions from the Orkhun-Yenisei monuments: "the order is without knowledge - the minister is also ignorant" (KT, 35). If it is assumed that issuing orders, commands and decrees in the affairs of power is primarily the authority of the chief ruler - the khagan, it is noteworthy that this *istilah* meaning "minister" is derived from the verb order. Also, in the studies, command is interpreted as a plural form and in the sense of "commander with a high task".

Istilah "in the texts of the Uyghur period, in the form of *buryuq* (undergoing metathesis) gained a lower level than *bäg* and a higher level than *mänč*". This can be observed in the following sentences: "*bäggärü ötunti ol buryuqi* - *buryuq* (ordered) bowed to the beg" (OY, 638/1); "letters are stitched, belts are pillars, pillars are backs - wives, princes, beggars, orders (ministers), beliefs, supports" (OY, 417/1). The fact that the name of this title is derived from the verb "to order" is certainly related to his position in management. Therefore, "in addition to the chief ruler in the khanate, the official who gives the main orders - the ministers are called orders" shows that they had a great position in government affairs and were authorized to issue the main orders and decrees related to the affairs of the government. Makhmud Koshghari uses *buyruq* in the form of a command and describes it as the person closest to the khagan according to his rank as "the person who transfers the adults to their place next to the king" and shows that he is originally a command - a commander. Because according to its meaning, he notes that he gave orders to those below him in some work (DLT, I, 316, 359).

In "Kutadgu bilig" the words *buyruq* (in the same place) and *bidir* are mentioned in the meaning and function of the writings: "*Yämä yahşi aymış bu türk işmiş - Say again, this is a Turkish person*" (QBK, 50), "*Yaraglig äränkä* ordered work - assigned the task to a trusted person" (QBK, 6).

When talking about the main reasons for the rise of the state in the ancient Turkish chronicles, it is not the khagans but other officials, it is the ministers who are *bilga* (wise) khagan, *alp* (bahodir) khagan, and *buyruqs*(ministers) are also described in terms of *bilga* and *alp ekkan*. As the main culprits of the decline, both the khagans and the ministers were accused of being uninformed (ignorant) khagans, and being lazy (bad) khagans, and their orders were also ignorant and coward (KT, 101-103). A. Donuk interprets the term *buyruq* as "member of the government" (minister) and says that it means "a high-ranking official appointed centrally to regulate the administrative and military affairs of the communities subordinate to him". Also, this word is used in the sense of "a civil servant who is responsible for the performance of military or civil duties and works under the command of the Khagan".

A high-ranking honorary military-administrative title (member of the state council) was mentioned in the inscription of Bilga Khagan: "*ulayu şadapit bağlar ... ataman tarkan, Tonyuquq, boyla бага tarkan - then shadapit ... ataman Tarkhan, Tonyuquq, Boyla Baga Tarkhan*" (BX, 14); "Knowing Tönyuquq, along with the Ältariş gagan boys, with Tarkhan and Eltarish Khan" (Ton, 6-7). J. Clawson said that "the title of *boyla* existed even in the Huns' era and was considered a rank close to the khakhan". From this, it can be said that it was one of the honorary titles with a relatively large and high position in the state administration. If you look carefully at the inscriptions, it can be seen that it is mainly used together with the name of khagan, a high-ranking official. For example, the Chinese historian writes that "*Boyla Tarkhan* was among the top officials around the Uyghur Khan in the (Middle) Persian document on Le Joq's second Turfan trip". In addition, "the first Khagan of Uyghurs was known as Fei-lo - *Boyla*" and the name of one of Uyghur princes was *Kutlug Boyla*. This title continued to be used in the Turkic associations formed in the far western regions of the Khaganate. In particular, in the 8th-10th centuries, "the existence of a title named after this *istilah* is recorded in the Bulgar Khanate".

Holders of this title are also entrusted with diplomatic powers as trustees of the Khagan. In the 10th century, the Byzantine emperor "K. Porfigrognnetos" work "De Keimononis" shows the combination of *içirgöy boyla – içirgü boyla – iç boyla*.

One of the highest military-administrative officials after the Khagan was ruled by *Yabgu*. The term *yabgu* was used from the Huns of Asia to Seljuk period. The title of *yabgu* was given to a person who is next to the khagan and who manages a certain part of khagan's territory and belongs to ruler's house. The title is mentioned in the epitaph of Mo'yun Chor: "*äki ogulima: yabgu: şad at bärtilim - I gave the title of yabgu and shad to my two sons*" (MCh, 19). Here it is said that the second son of Moyun Chor Khagan (747-759) appointed *Yabgu* and *Shad* to Tardush and Tolas tribes.

Even before the Turkic khanate was divided into two - the Eastern Turkic khanate and the Western Turkic khanate, "the first of its two parts had the position of central power and was ruled by the supreme ruler - the khagan, and the western part by the ruler with the title of *yabgu* or *yabgu-khagan* managed on behalf of the khagan". There is information in Chinese sources that Bumin Khagan was first mentioned with the title of *Yabgu*. "Before Bumin Khan, his grandfather Tu-wu was known as Ta Shih-hu, which is the Chinese form of this title, meaning "The Great

Yabgu'. Bumin Khagan's younger brother "The Western Blue Turkic people under Istami Yabgu-Khagan (552-576) were called "Yabgu Turks" in the sources". In the Khaganate, only persons related to the Khagan could attain the title of Yabgu, but later this tradition was lost. This idea is proved by the fact that the governors of the *khakims* formed in later periods were called by the same name. The term yabgu continued to be used during the Karakhanid era. However, Mahmud Koshgari states that this title in the form of yafgu "is used for a person who is two degrees below the khagan (of the people)" (DLT, III, 39-18). This information probably belongs to the early periods of the Karakhanid dynasty. This title can also be seen in the name of the founder of the Uighur state, Qutlugh Bilga Kul Khagan (745-747). In the 10th century, the Oghuz along Syrdarya River used the title of Yabgu as the title of the ruler.

An important position in the diplomatic relations of the ancient Turks - one of the titles is *yalabaç* - "ambassador; attaché". The term means "ambassador" in the scriptures. "Yalabaçi ädgü Sabi ötügi kälmäz täyin yayın süladim - the messenger, his good word, rumble did not come, so I made an army in the summer" (BX, 39). The lexeme is also used in "Kutadgu bilig" in the form of *yalavaç* and with the same meaning: "*Bu yañlig yalavaç tiläkkä tägir - such ambassadors will reach a wish*" (QBN, 1969; QBN, 2598). In the early sources, this word means a representative - an ambassador between two peoples, nations or states, and later it was also used to refer to a prophet (God's messenger on earth). Makhmud Koshgari noted that the ambassador of the ruler is called by the name of Yalafar in Uighurs (DLT, III, 334).

One of the terms meaning a person's name and title is *makaraç*: "*On aq oglum Türgäş kaganta Makaraç tamgaçi ... kälti - From my ten-arrow son (from) Turgash khagan Makarach tamgachi ... came*" (KT, 53). In the above sentence, the term *makarach* means the name of the sealer who came to the funeral of Kul Tegin from the Ten Arrows tribe. This title, which means "ruler" in Sanskrit and Tokharch, is embodied as a title of a position close to the ruler in the ancient Turkic peoples and their related peoples.

Another military-departmental title, *sāñün* - "commander" is found in the inscriptions of Bilga Khagan and Kul Tegin: "*Ku sāñün başadu tört tumän su kälti - forty thousand soldiers came under the leadership of commander Ku*"; "Commander Chang, the nephew of the Chinese emperor, came to *Tabgaç ghagan čiqanı Čan Sāñün*" (Ton, 53). *Istilah* is mentioned in twenty-three places in ancient Turkish texts in this meaning and function.

The term *tarkan* meaning "military chief, viceroy" is mentioned in Western Turkic and Uighur writings: "*İnanču apa yargan tarkan atig (birtim) - Inanchu Apa Yargan Tarkhan's horse (I gave)*" (KT, Ks): "*apa tarqangaru ičrä sab idmiš - sent a secret message to Apatar Khan (commander-in-chief)*" (Ton, 34). Also, the title Bilga Khagan is mentioned in combination with another title: "*ulayu šadapit bäglär ... ataman tarqan, Tonyuquq, boyla бага tarqan - then shadapit ... ataman Tarkhan, Tonyuquq, Boyla Baga Tarkhan*" (BX, 14). According to R. Jiro, the term *Tarqan* is a combination of two titles without the name of a specific person. It can be seen from the sources that the *tarqan* viceroy stands out as a middle-level military title. In particular, in the central administration of the Western Turkic Khanate, military officials were called by the names of *čabiš*, *tutug*, and *targan*. Also, it is known that the term "*tarqan*" was used in the state of Juan-juan, the title of "*tarqan*" was given to the descendants of the khagan, and it was recorded in Chinese annals about the Turks.

A. Donuk, the word *tarkan* means "high nobility level" in the Turkic Turks, "representative, minister" in the Uighurs, the owner of the rank after the commander-in-chief in the 10th century

Oghuz, "Hudud al-Olam" in the *Khazars*, according to the title of ruler (Tarkhan Khaqan). According to Ibn Hurdodbeh (IX), he writes that it means the rank next to the rulers. The title was used in the ancient language as a tribal name in the form of Tarjan in the Magyar language, and in the *Khazars* in the form of *Tarjan*, it also meant "commander, deputy". The Mongolian root of the name *darkha* means "privilege due to duty or success". In this place, *tarkhan* and *darkha* are not free of mutual relations. The Mongolian word *darkhan* means "shopkeeper, craftsman, exempt from taxes and official duties, holy for religious reasons". The word distribution mentioned in the scriptures is the plural form of *tarkan*.

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Conditional abbreviations
31. BX – Bilga Khagan inscription
32. DLT - Devonu dictionary-Turkish
33. DTS – Old Turkic dictionary
34. KCH - Kulichor inscription
35. KT - Kul Tegin epitaph
36. MCH - Moyun Chor inscription
37. NAL - Dictionary of Navoi's works
38. OTIL - an explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language
39. QBH, QBK – Yusuf Khos Hajib. "Kutadgu Bilig" S. Cairo copy (Dāru'l-kutub wa'l-vasā'iki'l-kawmiyya Sufism Turki 168. Nr)
40. QTT - Ancient Turkic language (the work of G. Abdurakhmanov and others)
41. Ton - Tunyukuk inscription